

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Nickel(II) with Salicylideneamino-carboxylic Acids and N-donor Ligands

REBATI C. DAS*, MIHIR K. MISHRA and SANGRAM K. MOHANTY

Department of Chemistry, Univ. College of Engineering, Burla-768 018, Orissa

Manuscript received 13 November 1979, accepted 20 December 1979

Mono- and diamine adducts of salicylideneaminocarboxylate complexes of nickel (II) have been prepared and analysed by elemental, molar conductance, magnetic moment, infra-red and electronic spectral analyses. The compounds have the compositions $NiSA.L_2$ (where L=monoamines like pyridine (Py), α -picoline (α -pic), γ -picoline (γ -pic), quinoline (Q) and triethylamine (Et_3N) and $NiSA.L'.nH_2O$ (where L' =ethylenediamine (en), *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*-pd), *o*, *o'*-bipyridyl (bp) and *o*-phenanthroline (*o*-phen) with SA^{--} =salicylidene-glycinate (Sg^{--}) or salicylideneanthranilate (Sa^{--}). All the compounds are found to be dimeric octahedral complexes using a bidentate carboxylic bridge.

THIS work has been undertaken as a part of our systematic work on the salicylideneamino-carboxylate complexes of bi- and trivalent metal ions and their adducts with various heterodonor. Such compounds have many interesting structural, magnetic, spectroscopic and other properties¹⁻³. Theriot *et al*¹ have prepared the diaquosalicylidene-glycinatonickel(II) and reported its composition, magnetic moment and electronic spectrum. This paper reports the properties of the compounds formed by the reaction of various monoamines viz. pyridine (py), α -picoline (α -pic), γ -picoline (γ -pic), quinoline (Q), triethylamine (Et_3N) and diamines viz. ethylenediamine (en), *o*, *o'*-bipyridyl (bp), *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*-pd) and *o*-phenanthroline (*o*-phen) with the Ni(II) complexes of salicylidene-glycine (H_2Sg) and salicylideneanthranilic acid (H_2Sa).

Experimental

Materials: All chemicals used were of pure/AnalaR grade. Methanol used as solvent was purified by standard method⁴. The compounds were prepared in the same way as the corresponding compounds of Cu(II) described elsewhere³.

Methods: Magnetic susceptibility of the compounds have been determined by Gouy method from solid specimen using $CoHg(NCS)_4$ and $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as standards. Molar conductance has been determined in $10^{-3}M$ methanolic solutions using Phillips conductivity bridge. Infra-red spectra of the compounds have been recorded between 4000 to 600 cm^{-1} . Similarly electronic spectra have been recorded in the region 50,000 cm^{-1} to 6,000 cm^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

Results of analysis and other physical data are recorded in Table 1. Molar conductance data (<13 mhos cm^2 mole⁻¹) indicate non-electrolytic nature of the compounds.

The TIP corrected magnetic moments are found to be in the range 3.13-3.35 BM per nickel atom. The values are consistent with high-spin octahedral configuration for the Ni(II) ion. The spin-orbit coupling constant (λ) lies in the range 267-309 cm^{-1} against free ion value (λ_0) of 324 cm^{-1} ^{4,5}

The compounds contain modified infra-red absorptions of both the starting complexes [salicylidene-glycinatonickel(II) and salicylideneanthranilatonickel(II)] and the heteroligands indicating the formation of mixed ligand complexes. The $\nu(N-H)$ vibrations are clearly observable from the spectra of the ethylenediamine and *o*-phenylenediamine adducts within 3220-3300 cm^{-1} . The bipyridyl adduct of salicylidene-glycinatonickel(II) has a broad band at 3550 cm^{-1} which may be due to the $\nu(O-H)$ vibration of the lattice water molecule. The $\nu(C=N)$ vibrations of the azomethine groups appear at 1602-1630 cm^{-1} either separately or mixed with other vibrations in that region. This is at a lower energy region than those of the free Schiff-base ligands. The $\nu(C-O)$ (phenolic) band occurs at 1310-1330 cm^{-1} which is about 20-40 cm^{-1} higher than that due to the free Schiff-bases indicating monodentate nature of the phenolic oxygen atom⁷. For a bidentate or bridging phenolic group, this vibration occurs at a considerable higher frequency^{8,9}, ~ 1550 cm^{-1} . The asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylate groups, $\nu_{as}(COO^-)$ and $\nu_s(COO^-)$, occur at 1570-1590 and 1472-1485 cm^{-1}

TABLE 1— ANALYSES, MELTING POINT, MAGNETIC MOMENT, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	Colour	Form	Analyses ^a		μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Δ_M (mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹)	Ligand field bands in methanol(in cm ⁻¹)			
			%Ni	%N			ν_1^c	ν_2^c	ν_3^a	ν_4^a
[NiSg(Py) ₂] ₂	Light-green	Crystalline	15.0 (14.90)	10.6 (10.66)	3.26	6.5	11,000 (39.4)	17,545 (31.6)	(17,525)	(28,250)
[NiSg(α -pic) ₂] ₂	Green	-do-	14.0 (13.91)	10.0 (9.95)	3.31	7.6	10,925 (16.3)	17,390 (25.6)	(17,355)	(28,250)
[NiSg(ν -pic) ₂] ₂	Bluish-green	Micro-crystalline	13.8 (13.91)	10.1 (9.95)	3.13	6.8	10,930 (14.5)	17,390 (18.6)	(17,125)	(28,400)
[NiSgQ ₂] ₂	Green	Crystalline	11.6 (11.89)	8.5 (8.51)	3.13	8.0	9990 (21.2)	15,505 (31.6)	(15,535)	(25,650)
[NiSg(Et ₃ N) ₂] ₂	Light-green	Micro-crystalline	12.9 (13.41)	9.6 (9.60)	3.18	10.5	9970 (21.2)	15,670 (25.5)	(15,610)	(25,515)
[NiSa(Py) ₂] ₂	Yellowish-green	Crystalline	12.9 (12.88)	9.2 (9.21)	3.35	7.8	11,050 (25.7)	17,095 (37.6)	(17,110)	(27,050)
[NiSa(α -pic) ₂] ₂	Yellow	-do-	11.8 (12.13)	8.8 (8.68)	3.34	8.7	11,000 (16.5)	17,545 (15.3)	(17,525)	(28,250)
[NiSa(ν -pic) ₂] ₂	Light-yellow	Micro-crystalline	12.1 (12.13)	8.7 (8.68)	3.27	6.7	10,850 (16.7)	16,050 (22.3)	(16,080)	(27,175)
[NiSaQ ₂] ₂	Yellowish-green	Crystalline	10.3 (10.56)	7.6 (7.56)	3.26	8.7	10,000 (34.4)	16,530 (39.5)	(16,480)	(26,420)
[NiSa(Et ₃ N) ₂] ₂	Light-green	Micro-crystalline	11.5 (11.75)	8.5 (8.40)	3.36	10.8	9970 (27.3)	15,870 (30.8)	(15,845)	(25,430)
[NiSg en] ₂	Brick-red	Crystalline	19.5 (19.85)	14.0 (14.20)	3.19	11.6	11,000 (15.6)	17,545 (16.6)	(17,528)	(28,260)
[NiSg(o-pd)] ₂	Blue	Crystalline	16.7 (17.08)	12.1 (12.22)	3.21	12.3	10,500 (25.6)	16,815 (30.5)	(16,800)	(27,290)
[NiSg(bp)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O ^b	Green	Micro-crystalline	14.2 (14.32)	10.1 (10.25)	3.29	8.5	10,600	17,390	(17,020)	(29,285)
[NiSg(o-phen)] ₂	Light-green	Crystalline	14.0 (14.12)	9.6 (10.10)	3.33	9.5	10,985 (35.9)	17,515 (30.0)	(17,490)	(28,200)
[NiSa en] ₂	Buff	-do-	15.9 (16.41)	11.8 (11.74)	3.24	11.2	11,020 (10.8)	17,480 (12.4)	(17,450)	(28,050)
[NiSa(o-pd)] ₂	Light-pink	Micro-crystalline	14.3 (14.47)	10.3 (10.35)	3.23	12.8	10,750 (51.8)	16,385 (58.5)	(16,395)	(25,720)
[NiSa(bp)] ₂	Yellowish-green	-do-	13.0 (12.94)	9.2 (9.26)	3.27	9.3	10,500 (14.4)	16,815 (19.3)	(16,800)	(27,300)
[NiSa(o-phen)] ₂	Yellowish-green	Crystalline	11.8 (12.29)	8.6 (8.79)	3.33	7.8	10,500 (46.5)	17,285 (53.8)	(17,245)	(29,546)

- a. Figures in parentheses show the calculated values. (ν_2 calculated by procedure of Lever¹², ν_3 calculated by procedures of Lever¹² and Underhill and Billing¹³)
- b. %H₂O 4.2 (found), 4.39 (calculated).
- c. Figures in parentheses are molar extinction coefficients.

respectively with a difference, $\Delta\nu$ (COO⁻), of 95-105 cm⁻¹. A free ionic carboxylate group⁷ usually has a $\Delta\nu$ (COO⁻) of \approx 200 cm⁻¹. A monodentate carboxylate group⁷ has a difference of 150-180 cm⁻¹, but a bidentate or bridging carboxylate has a much closer difference (<120 cm⁻¹)^{10,11}. Bridging carboxylate groups are, therefore, indicated in the present compounds.

The lowest energy ligand field transition occurs at 9,970-11,765 cm⁻¹ which may be taken as ν_1 (10Dq) band corresponding to ³A_{2g} → ⁸T_{2g} transition of nickel(II) under octahedral symmetry. The ν_2 band corresponding to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) transition occurs at 15,505-17,545 cm⁻¹. The ν_2/ν_1 ratio ranges between 1.48-1.65 which is close to 1.6 expected for octahedral Ni(II) complexes. In some compounds another band of very low intensity occurs in between these two bands (12,500-13,570

cm⁻¹) which may be due to spin-forbidden ³A_{2g} → ¹E_g(D) transition. The ν_3 band [³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P)] position of the complexes has been calculated from their ν_1 and ν_2 band positions by the procedures of Lever¹² and Underhill and Billing¹³. The calculated value of ν_3 position is within the range 25,450-29,500 cm⁻¹. This band could not be seen separately because it gets masked by intense charge transfer bands in that region. A weak band, usually occurring as a shoulder to the nearby charge-transfer band, is seen in some compounds at 20,600-23,400 cm⁻¹ which may be due to spin-forbidden ³A_{2g} → ¹T_{2g}(G) transition. The Racah parameter (B) has been calculated to be between 565 to 1019. The nephelauxetic parameter (β_{3s}) is within 0.62-0.81.

In view of the above analytical, spectral, magnetic moment and other data all the compounds may be inferred to be dimeric and octahedral in

structure containing bidentate carboxylate groups and four monoamine molecules or two diamine molecules in the co-ordination sphere (Fig. 1 & 2).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their gratitude to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Government of Orissa for supporting the research scheme.

References

1. L. J. THERIOT, G. C. CARLISLE and H. J. HU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 2841, 2891, 3303.
2. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Progr. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **7**, 83.
3. R. C. DAS, M. K. MISHRA and S. K. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 170.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "Elementary Practical Organic Chemistry, Part I" (Longman, Green and Co., London), 1957.
5. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields" (Interscience, New York), 1966.
6. S. V. LAKSHMAN and J. L. RAO, *Indian J. Pure and Appl. Phys.*, 1971, **9**, 139.
7. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Co-ordination Compounds" (John Wiley, New York), 1966.
8. T. TOKII, Y. MUTO, M. KATO, K. IMAI and H. B. JONASSEN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 1539.
9. R. K. MEHTA and R. K. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 56.
10. N. F. CURTIS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1579.
11. K. DEY and K. C. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 66.
12. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", (Elsevier Publ., New York), 1968.
13. A. E. UNDERHILL and D. E. BILLING, *Nature*, 1966, **210**, 834.